

The Impact of Transition to the Application of IFRS 15: Recognition of Revenue from Contracts with Customers a Case Study (Jordan Telecommunication's Company – Orange -)

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Abstract

The study aims to examine the effect of transition to the application of IFRS 15: recognition of revenues from contracts with customers in Jordanian telecommunications' companies, as a case study it was conducted in Jordan Telecommunications Company (Orange) for the period between 2010-2017, The researchers re-calculated the revenue of contracts with customers retroactively, and separate the goods' revenues from services' revenues, also calculate the assets from contracts at the end of each interim period for the quarterly progress reports for all periods of study. A number of statistical methods were used; the most important one is descriptive statistics, the natural distribution of data and testing the study hypotheses using the multiple regression equations to identify the effect of independent variables on dependent variables. The most important result of the study showed that there is a statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) for the application of IFRS 15 as measured by the services' revenue, goods' revenue, and contract assets on total revenues and owner equity, The study recommended urging the telecommunications companies working in Jordan especially Orange to apply IFRS 15 for its impact to achieve transparency in disclosure, and to increase the reliability of accounting measurement of financial reporting.

Key Words: IFRS 15: Revenue from Contracts with Customers, Contract Assets, Services' Revenue, goods' Revenue, Orange, Telecommunications Companies.

Introduction

Requirements of recognition according to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) that issued by International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) differ from requirements of United States Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (US-GAAP) that issued by Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB), both requirements need to be reviewed and developed since the limited requirements included in the standards that do not cover all related issues and topics.

According to IFRSs, two standards discussed revenues' matters, IAS 11: Construction Contracts and IAS 18: Revenues, but it is very difficult to apply those standards to all types of revenues, especially the complicated financial transactions, besides not all cases of revenues mentioned in the two standards, because of that IASB in associated with FASB determine the requirements of financial reporting related to revenues in one standard, IASB issued in May 2015 IFRS 15: revenues from contracts with customers, it is expected that IFRS 15 resulted in revolution in accounting since it supersedes sixth issuances: IAS 11: Construction Contracts and IAS 18: Revenues, IFRIC 13: Customer Loyalty Programmes, IFRIC 15: Agreements for the Construction of Real Estate, IFRIC 18: Transfers of Assets from Customers, and SIC 31: Revenue Barter Transaction Involving Advertising.

Literature Review

IFRS 15 establish the principles that an entity shall apply to report useful information to users of financial statements about the nature, amount, timing, and uncertainty of revenue and cash flows arising from a contract with a customers, also deletes the spatiality of revenue recognition in some types of industries through set a general criteria for revenue recognition consists of five steps, those are (IFRS 15, IN7):

- Identify the contract(s) with a customer
- Identify the performance obligations in the contract
- Determine the transaction price
- Allocate the transaction price to the performance obligations in the contract

- Recognize revenue when (or as) the entity satisfies a performance obligation.

Chapple and others look to the application of IFRIC 13: Customer Loyalty Programmes that superseded by IFRS 15: Revenue from Contracts with Customers enhances the ability of changing the financial results and the ability of using IFRIC 13 for the profit management purposes during economic crises, while Abu Romman(2014) found out less commitment of Jordanian construction companies in applying superseded IAS 11: Construction Contracts and IAS 18: Revenues, in preparation of financial statements, also Jordanian construction companies face accounting problems prevent applying of IFRSs, those problems such as the instability in accounting measurement basics and continuous amendments in it, Nulla(2014) look to the adoption of IFRSs in communications' companies resulted in reduction of the ability to forecast revenues in these companies, negative change in market prices, and enhancing ability cash flows forecasting and financial expectations, decreasing in accruals, and missing the timeliness of revenue recognition, increase in fair market value, increase in profit evaluation, and increase in operating ability and forecasting ability, Lakhmees(2014) assured the disability of construction contracts in Egypt to adopt IFRS 15.

Problem of the study and its questions

Researchers will investigate the possibility of applying IFRS 15 in Jordanian telecommunications companies, through case study in Jordanian telecommunications company (Orange), and determine the impact of applying IFRS 15 on total revenues and owner equity, and identify the practical and professional obstacles that may be took place as a result of applying the standard, since there are a special issues related to revenue recognition in telecommunications companies as a service companies timeliness of revenue recognition, and the like, these issues such as: determine the recognized revenues from prepaid cards, that initially must be recognized as a liability, the revenue will be recognized in case of using card or at ending of expiry date whichever comes first, other issue relates to accompanying of perfuming communication service with granting mobiles to customers, or performing other services freely or by discounts, with commitment to specific period of time, also the companies grant internet service in the form of annual contracts with free monthly fees according to the extent of customer commitment with the company.

The study will investigate the way of revenue recognition in telecommunications companies according to the new requirements included in IFRS 15, so the problem of the study may be questioned as follow:

First question: Is there an impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)? this question includes the following sub questions:

1. Is there an impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from services on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)?
2. Is there an impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from selling goods on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)?
3. Is there an impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by assets from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)?

Second question: Is there an impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)? this question includes the following sub questions:

1. Is there an impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from services on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)?
2. Is there an impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from selling goods on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)?

3. Is there an impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by assets from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)?

Research Hypotheses:

According to the questions of the study, researchers developed the following hypotheses:

HO1: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)? this hypotheseis includes the following sub hypotheses:

HO1a: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from services on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

HO1b: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from selling goods on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

HO1c: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by assets from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

HO2:there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange)? this hypothesis includes the following sub hypotheses:

HO2a: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from services on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

HO2b: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from selling goods on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

HO2c: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by assets from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Objectives of the study:

The study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).
2. Determine the impact of application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from services on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).
3. Determine the impact of application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from selling goods on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).
4. Determine the impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by assets from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

5. Determine the impact of application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).
6. Determine the impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from services on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).
7. Determine the impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from selling goods on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).
8. Determine the impact to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by assets from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Importance of the study:

The importance of the study derived from the importance of telecommunication industry in Jordan, since in the last decade this industry achieved accelerated development, also it has an increased role in economic development, telecommunication industry achieved the first rank between highest sectors contribution in gross product to economic sectors, its contribution in Gross Domestic Production(GDP) is 5.12% according to studies conducted by General Statistics Department (GSD). Jordan considered to be the only country in Arab region that release completely the telecommunication market, in spite of fact that there are several challenges must be treated to develop the infra-structure to increase the efficiency of telecommunication sector and its competitiveness between business sectors, and secure better ability to increase users with high effective services with accepted economic cost (www.dose.gov.jo). Researchers look forward to determine the accounting matters that affect revenue recognition from customers, in order to contribute directly in enhancing the ability of telecommunication companies in high quality revenue recognition, that reflects on its performance, so the importance of the study could be divided in the following areas:

1. **Theoretical importance:** relate to clarify IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers, and identify its impact on statement on financial position, statement of profit or loss and other comprehensive income, in Jordanian telecommunications companies through case study in Jordanian telecommunications company (Orange).
2. **Practical importance:** relate to the necessity of telecommunications companies commitment to the standard since those companies represent an important part of Jordanian companies that must apply IFRSs according to item 184 of companies law 13 to 2003, researchers think that IFRS 15 will contribute in solving problems that face telecommunications industry for the purposes of increasing reliability in recognized revenues, also reduce those problems and difficulties that reflect positively on Jordanian economic in general.

Methodology of the study:

Researchers adopt inductive method in identifying the problem and set the hypotheses of the study, and conductive method in collection the data from the primary and secondary sources, also adopt historical method in discussing the literature review, in addition to descriptive analysis method for the scientific research depending on empirical method for collection of financial data that derived from financial statements and contracts with customers in Jordan telecommunication company for the interim financial reporting during the period between 2010 and 2017, in addition to disclosures that included in annual reports for the purposes of hypotheses testing, also researchers conduct structural interviews with related directors in order to identify the nature of revenues and its classifications in the company so as to determine the most influenced contracts.

Procedures of applying IFRS 15

Researchers studied contracts that signed with customers retroactively as follow:

1. studying the terms included in the contracts that meet the requirements on IFRS 15 to every business unit as follow:
 - a. Consumer Business Unit(CBU), total contracts are 31249.
 - b. Small and Medium Enterprise(PRO), total contracts are 2358 .
 - c. Enterprise Business Unit(EBU), total contracts are 10698.
2. Applying the five steps in IFRS 15 to contracts with customers as in the following example:

Orange co. signed a contract with a customer in 1/7/2016 for two years to benefit from the telecommunications service, the monthly fee is JD 20, the company will provide the customer with mobile free, its price is JD 150.

Step 1: Identifying the contract with customer: the signed contract for two years.

Step 2: Identifying performance commitments in the contract:

- including the customer in telecommunications service.
- Providing customer with mobile free

Step 3 : Determining the price of transaction:

Monthly fee is JD 20 for two years, with total fees equal to JD 240.

Step 4: Allocation the price of the transaction to performance commitments as it shown in the following schedule:

Performance commitments	Selling price	percentage	Revenue from selling price
Subscription fee	480.00	76%	365.71
Mobile	150.00	24%	114.29
Total	630.00	100%	480.00

Step 5: Recognition of Revenue when satisfying the performance commitments:

- When providing customer with mobile, the company journalize the transaction as follow:

Accrued revenues	114.29	
Mobile revenues		114.29

- When providing the service and collecting the revenue, the company journalize the transaction at the end of each month as follow:

Cash	20.00	
Revenue from subscription		15.24
Accrued revenue		4.76

2. Allocation of revenues separately between subscription fees and mobile as it shown in the following schedule:

Year	Subscription fee	Mobile revenue	Total
2016	91.44	28.56	120.00
2017	182.88	57.12	240.00
2018	91.44	28.56%	120.00
Total	365.76	114.24	480.00

4. Recognizing Contract assets at the end of the financial period in statement of financial position within current assets according to the requirements of IFRS 15 as it shown in the following schedule:

Year end	Contract asset
31/12/2016	360.00
31/12/2017	120.00
Total	480.00

5. Amending beginning balances for the related financial periods, by reflecting recalculated amounts from the current contracts in retained earnings according to the requirements of IFRS 15.
6. Identifying the practical problems that need to be applied retroactively according to IFRS 15 as follow:
- The huge amount of contracts that company required to improve accounting system so as to meet the requirements of IFRS 15 accurately.
 - The less coordination between employees about the importance of applying IFRS 15, to achieve that it a must to coordinate between related departments (marketing, sales, information technology, and accounting) to follow contracts and providing accounting department with these contracts in order to review it and be sure that contracts prepared according IFRS 15.
 - Employees misunderstanding to IFRS 15 and its requirements that needs intensive training to all issues included in the standard.
 - Absence of clear accounting policy for calculation of contracts cost and other related expenses that must be capitalized.

Testing of Hypotheses

In order to answer the questions of the study and test hypotheses, researchers used the following methods depending on Statistical Package For Social Sciences(SPSS):

1. **Descriptive Analysis:** like mean, standard deviation to determine the dispersion of variables and the highest and lowest values, the results may be discussed as shown in the following schedule (1):

Schedule 1 :Results of descriptive statistics to study variables

Variable's	Mean	Std. Deviation	Maximum	Minimum
Services revenues	768 365	111 050	838 707	277 008
Goods revenues	45 682	14 379	100 280	34 626
Assets of contracts with customers	4,390,766	910,578	6 932 529	3 462 596
Total revenues	92 806 189	8 540 328	108 456 389	79 778 431
Owner equity	354 328 738	51 127 511	442 042 427	225 988 308

The above schedule shows descriptive analysis for revenues from contracts with customers, and separate it to services revenues and goods revenues that presented in statement of profit or loss and other comprehensive income in total without any related disclosures within notes to financial statements,

researchers separate it according to requirements of IFRS 15 because its materiality, the arithmetic mean to services' revenues equal to JD 768 365, with standard deviation equal to JD 111 050, while the arithmetic mean to goods' revenues equal to JD 45 682 with standard deviation equal to JD 14 379, if we compare services revenues to goods revenues, it is noticed that the highest value belongs to services revenues since Orange as other telecommunication companies depends in generating revenues on performing services as a main activity other than selling goods like mobiles and internet modems, researchers recalculated assets from contracts with customers that calculated according to requirements of IAS 18 according IFRS 15, the arithmetic mean to services revenues equal to JD 4 390 766 with standard deviation equal to JD 910 578, that indicates to large amount of contracts with customers, it can be justified by application of requirements of IFRS 15 relate to present this value separate in statement of financial position within current assets. Also the schedule (1) shows owner equity with arithmetic mean equal to JD 354 328 738 with standard deviation equal to JD 51 127 511, the highest amount to owner equity is JD 442 042 427, refers to the first quarter of 2010, while the lowest amount to owner equity is JD 225 988 308, refers to the second quarter of 2016, in addition, the schedule (1) shows the total revenues with arithmetic mean equal to JD 92 806 189 with standard deviation equal to JD 8 540 328, the highest amount to total revenues is JD 108 456 389, refers to the third quarter of 2011, while the lowest amount to total revenues is JD 79 778 431, refers to the first quarter of 2015.

2. Examining the validity of data for the purposes of statistical analysis and relevance of data to the normal distribution by using Kolmogorov-Smirnov, and multicollinearity test, the results as it shown in schedule(2)

Schedule (2): normal distribution

Variable's	df	K-S (Statistic)	Sig
Services revenues	29	0.416	0.069
Goods revenues	29	0.679	0.059
Assets of contracts with customers	29	0.977	0.080
Total revenues	29	0.779	0.068
Owner equity	29	0.520	0.073

The above schedule shows the results of the extent to variable to be closed from its normal distribution, the normal logarithms of service revenue, goods revenue, and assets from contracts with customers, represents the independent variables, while normal logarithm of: total revenues, and owner equity represents the dependent variable, to be sure that variables of the study follow the normal distribution, **Sig** must exceeds 5%, the schedule shows that **Sig** for all variable exceeds 5%, that indicate to availability of normal distribution in the variables, and multiple regression can be used.

Multicollinearity test: according to the results of normal distribution, researchers also conducted the possibility of using the two models of the study for statistical analysis through Multicollinearity and Tolerance, the results as it shown in schedule (3) Schedule (3): Multicollinearity test

The first model of the study to the first hypothesis		
Independent Variables	Multicollinearity	
	VIF	Tolerance
service revenue	1.896	0.775
goods revenue	2.755	0.439
assets of contracts with customers	3.918	0.612
Durbin-Watson	1.664	
The first model of the study to the second hypothesis		
Multicollinearity	Multicollinearity	
	VIF	Tolerance
service revenue	1.019	0.578
goods revenue	2.748	0.644
assets of contracts with customers	3.918	0.392
Durbin-Watson	1.981	

In order to clarify what is included in the schedule above,)VIF (*Variance Inflationary Factor* must be considered, in case of (*VIF*) equal or more than 5%, there is inflation (Field, 2001) (Myrs, 1990), the multicollinearity also represented if *Tolerance* less than 10%, the schedule shows that the two models of the study passed the two tests.

3. Testing hypotheses of the study by using Multiple Regression Analysis to identify the impact of independent variables on dependent variable.

Researchers use multiple regression analysis to test the first hypothesis and related sub hypotheses, they depend on value of significance since this value must be less than 5% to reject the hypotheses, other than, the hypotheses must be accepted, also they depend of calculated *T* , that its absolute value must be exceeds its scheduled value at *Sig* ≤ 0.05, in order to interpret dependent variable by the independent variable, the researchers used *Adjusted R Square*, the following schedule shows the results of testing the first main hypothesis

H01: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange) this hypothesis includes the following sub hypothesis:

Schedule (4): results of testing the first main hypothesis

$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * X_1 + \beta_2 * X_2 + \beta_3 * X_3 + e$				
<i>Model</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>Constant</i>	40.975	6.476	0.000
<i>X₁(services revenues)</i>	2.528	0.711	5.631	0.012
<i>X₂(goods revenues)</i>	1.055	0.343	6.318	0.029
<i>X₃(assets from contracts with customers)</i>	1.190	0.370	3.780	0.001
F test Model= 14.277		Sig F= 0.000		
F Distribution Table = 2.781		T Distribution Table=1.669		
Adjusted R Square= 0.587		R= 0.795		

Y_1 indicates the dependent variable, it represents the normal logarithm to total revenues, X_1 indicates the normal logarithm to services revenues, X_2 indicates the normal logarithm to goods revenues, X_3 indicates the normal logarithm to assets from contracts with customers as independent variables.

The above schedule shows the results of testing the first hypothesis by using multiple regression test to apply IFRS 15 that measured by services revenues, goods revenues, and assets from contracts with customers as independent variables, and its impact on total revenues as dependent variable, data included in the schedule show that *Sig F= 0.000* , it is less than 5%, beside calculated *F* equal to 14.277, which is more than scheduled *F* that equal to 2.781, the result is reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, that says: there is an statistical at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) impact to application of IFRS 15 on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company, in addition, the study model has a high interpretation possibility, depending on value of outcomes of calculated *x* that its value more than scheduled *x*, which supported by no multicollinearity as mentioned in schedule (3).

Also, the schedule shows that correlation coefficient(*R*)= 0.795 assures that there is a high positive relation ship between applying of IFRS 15 measured by services revenues, goods revenues, and assets from contracts with customers and total revenues, in addition, the schedule shows that Adjusted R Square equal to 0.587, that means 58.7% from changes in total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange), explained by changes caused by applying of IFRS 15.

Relating to testing of sub hypotheses to the first main hypothesis, results come as follow:

HO1a: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from services on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Results of testing this hypothesis clarify that Coefficient equal to 0.711, that indicates to statistical positive relationship between independent variable (application of IFRS 15) measured by services revenues and independent variable (total revenues), that means total revenues increase by applying of IFRS 15, **Sig** equal to 0.012 indicates to statistical impact since its value less than 0.05, that is supported by calculated **T** that its value equal to 5.631 while scheduled **T** equal to 1.669 with degree of freedom equal to 29, as a result first sub-null hypothesis rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted, that indicates to existence of statistical impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15 measured by services revenues on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

HO1b: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by goods revenues on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Results of testing this hypothesis clarify that Coefficient equal to 0.343, that indicates to statistical positive relationship between independent variable (application of IFRS 15) measured by goods revenues and independent variable (total revenues), that means total revenues increase by applying of IFRS 15, **Sig** equal to 0.029 indicates to statistical impact since its value less than 0.05, that is supported by calculated **T** that its value equal to 6.318 while scheduled **T** equal to 1.669 with degree of freedom equal to 29, as a result second sub-null hypothesis rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted, that indicates to existence of statistical impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to applying of IFRS 15 measured by goods' revenues on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

HO1c: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by assets from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Results of testing this hypothesis clarify that Coefficient equal to 0.370, that indicates to statistical positive relationship between independent variable (application of IFRS 15) measured by assets from contracts with customers and independent variable (total revenues), that means total revenues increase by applying of IFRS 15, **Sig** equal to 0.000 indicates to statistical impact since its value less than 0.05, that is supported by calculated **T** that value equal to 3.780 while scheduled **T** equal to 1.669 with degree of freedom equal to 29, as a result third sub-null hypothesis rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted, that indicates to existence of statistical impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to applying of IFRS 15 measured by assets from contracts with customers on total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

According to for mentioned discussion, the equation of multiple regression that represents the model of forecasting of total revenues in Jordanian telecommunication company in case of applying IFRS 15 can be drawn as follow:

$$Y_1 = 40.975 + 2.528 * X_1 + 1.055 * X_2 + 1.190 * X_3 + e$$

Which:

Y_1 : represents the dependents variable which is normal logarithm to total revenues

X_1 : represents the independents variable which is normal logarithm to services revenues.

X_2 :represents the independents variable which is normal logarithm to goods revenues.

X_3 :represents the independents variable which is normal logarithm to assets from contracts with customers.e :error.

HO2: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Schedule (5): results of testing the second main hypothesis ‘

$Y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * X_1 + \beta_2 * X_2 + \beta_3 * X_3 + e$				
<i>Model</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>Constant</i>	13.452	9.455	0.000
X_1 (services revenues)	0.560	0.805	4.607	0.012
X_2 (goods revenues)	0.497	0.201	5.804	0.033
X_3 (assets from contracts with customers)	0.355	0.180	2.592	0.016
F test Model= 8.791		Sig F= 0.000		
F Distribution Table = 2.781		T Distribution Table=1.669		
Adjusted R Square= 0.455		R= 0.716		

Y_1 indicates to dependent variable, it represents the normal logarithm to owner equity, X_1 indicates to the normal logarithm to services' revenues, X_2 indicates to the normal logarithm to goods' revenues, X_3 indicates to the normal logarithm to assets from contracts with customers as independent variables.

The above schedule includes the results of testing the second hypothesis by using multiple regression test to apply IFRS 15 that measured by services' revenues, goods' revenues, and assets from contracts with customers as independent variables, and its impact on owner equity as dependent variable, data included in the schedule show that **Sig F= 0.000**, it is less than 5%, beside calculated **F** equal to 8.791, which is more than scheduled **F** which equal to 2.781, so null hypothesis rejected and accept the alternative hypothesis, that means there is an statistical impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15 on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company(Orange), in addition, the study model has a high interpretation possibility, depending on value of outcomes of calculated x that its value more than scheduled x, which supported by no multicollinearity as mentioned in schedule (3).

Also, the schedule shows that correlation coefficient(R)= 0.716 assures that there is a high positive relationship between application of IFRS 15 measured by services' revenues, goods' revenues, and assets from contracts with customers and owner equity, in addition, the schedule shows that Adjusted R Square equal to 0.455, that means 44.5% from changes in owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange), explained by changes caused because of applying IFRS 15.

Relating to testing of sub hypotheses to the first main hypothesis, results come as follow:

HO2a: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by revenues from services on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Results of testing this hypothesis clarify that Coefficient equal to 0.405, that indicates to statistical positive relationship between independent variable (application of IFRS 15) measured by services revenues and dependent variable (owner equity), that means owner equity increase by applying IFRS 15, **Sig** equal to 0.012 indicates to statistical impact since its value less than 0.05, that is supported by calculated **T** that value equal to 4.607 while scheduled **T** equal to 1.669 with degree of freedom equal to 29, as a result first

sub-null hypothesis rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted, that indicates to existence of statistical impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15 measured by services revenues on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company(Orange).

HO2b: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by goods revenues on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Results of testing this hypothesis clarify that Coefficient equal to 0.201, that indicates to statistical positive relationship between independent variable (application of IFRS 15) measured by goods revenues and independent variable (owner equity), that means owner equity increase by applying of IFRS 15, **Sig** equal to 0.033 indicates to statistical impact since its value less than 0.05 , that is supported by calculated **T** that value equal to 5.804 while scheduled **T** equal to 1.669 with degree of freedom equal to 29, as a result second sub-null hypothesis rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted, that indicates to existence of statistical impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15 measured by goods revenues on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

HO2c: there is no significant statically impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to application of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by assets from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

Results of testing this hypothesis clarify that Coefficients equal to 0.180, that indicates to statistical positive relationship between independent variable (application of IFRS 15) measured by assets from contracts with customers and independent variable (owner equity), that means owner equity increase by applying of IFRS 15, **Sig** equal to 0.016 indicates to statistical impact since its value less than 0.05 , that is supported by calculated **T** that value equal to 3.780 while scheduled **T** equal to 1.669 with degree of freedom equal to 29, as a result third sub-null hypothesis rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted, that indicates to existence of statistical impact at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) to applying of IFRS 15 measured by assets from contracts with customers on owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company (Orange).

According to for mentioned discussion, the equation of multiple regression that represents the model of forecasting of owner equity in Jordanian telecommunication company(Orange) in case of applying IFRS 15 can be drawn as follow:

$$Y_1 = 13.452 + 0.560 * X_1 + 0.479 * X_2 + 0.355 * X_3 + e$$

Which:

Y₁: represents the dependents variable which is normal logarithm to owner equity .

X₁ : represents the independents variable which is normal logarithm to services revenues.

X₂ :represents the independents variable which is normal logarithm to goods revenues.

X₃ :represents the independents variable which is normal logarithm to assets from contracts with customers .
e :error.

Conclusion

Researchers concluded after data analysis and testing hypotheses that there is a significant statistical impact to applying of IFRS 15: revenue from contracts with customers measured by services' revenues, goods' revenues, and assets from contracts with customers on total revenues since the main business of the company relates to provide communication and internet services to its customers with performance commitments, also, the company according to requirements of IFRS 15 has to allocate revenues between goods and services when provide mobiles and other equipment freely or with discounts.

Also, researchers concluded that there is a significant statistical impact to applying of IFRS 15 on owner equity, since the company recognize assets from contracts with customers through capitalization of deferred revenues.

Researchers recommend that the company must focus on training its accountants and other financial employees so as to understand the requirements of IFRS 15, also the company must consider a requirement to IFRS 15 relates to the necessity of disclose how it allocates revenues between services performed and equipment provided in financial statements, beside presenting assets from contacts with customers within current assets in statement of financial position and determining the timeliness of revenue recognition.

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